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Frequently Asked Questions for Ambassadors

This document outlines the answers to the most frequently asked questions about the COcyber project's Ambassador programme.

About the project

What's COcyber?

COcyber is a European project –a coordination and support action– funded by the European Commission under the [European Cybersecurity Competence Centre](#) in the framework of the Digital Europe Programme. The project kicked off in July 2024 and will run for 24 months until June 2026. Through COcyber, 9 European partners have come together with the shared ambition of fostering European collaboration in civilian and defence digital safety.

To reach this goal, COcyber partners provide unique opportunities to develop an in-depth understanding of the state of collaboration in the civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors, while hosting a wide range of meetings and events for the cybersecurity community and stakeholders, including round-table discussions, workshops, and seminars. Moreover, the project aims to liaise with 20+ relevant initiatives and projects to leverage the ongoing efforts in the field across Europe.

Funded by
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Who is behind COcyber?

The project is implemented by [a multidisciplinary team](#) of 9 European partners.

- **28DIGITAL** (BE): COcyber's project coordinator.
- **The European Organisation for Security** (BE): managing the COcyber community of stakeholders.
- **The Lisbon Council** (BE): leading the COcyber online platform.
- **Université Libre de Brussels – Solvay Brussels School** (BE) – facilitating the exchange of knowledge and best practices between civilian and defence sectors.
- **AUSTRALO Marketing Lab** (ES) – Communication and Dissemination Leader.
- **AMETIC** (ES): leading the effort around synergies, sustainability and exploitation.
- **Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia** (SI), **Informatikai, Tavkozlesi Es Elektronikai Vallalkozasok Szovetsege** (HU) and **Asociacija Infobalt** (LT): each leading one of COcyber's national case studies.

About the Ambassador programme

Why does COcyber run an Ambassador Programme?

COcyber aims to ally the European civilian and defence cybersecurity communities by fostering knowledge sharing, harmonising European actions and proposing concrete tools for engagement and collaboration. To support our communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities, we run an **Ambassador programme that engages 15+ European professionals** actively participating in the European digital defence arena.

We recognize the value that the Ambassadors –onboarded external experts– can bring to the COcyber community in terms of widening COcyber's reach (e.g. public awareness) and increasing its impact (e.g. external stakeholders benefiting from our activities and results).

What is the role of the onboarded Ambassadors?

In general terms, the role of the COcyber Ambassadors is to:

- Create and share quality content related to civilian and defence cybersecurity topics.
- Increase COcyber's visibility on different online communication channels (e.g. social media and website).
- Speak about and endorse COcyber at relevant events with local, national and European stakeholders.

- Be informed, so they can communicate about the latest developments and impacts of the COcyber programme.
- Provide their insights and feedback to support further improvements of the COcyber ecosystem.

The following figure summarises the Ambassadors' role under Batch #3 (the third round of recruited Ambassadors) in 7 key actions.

Moreover, based on these actions, the COcyber team has defined a list of key performance indicators (KPIs) the appointed Ambassadors are asked to reach by the end of their Ambassadorship.

Action	Details
Individual Ambassador profiles on the COcyber website	Provide the necessary information to the COcyber team so they can publish your ambassador profile.
Contribute to an online interview	Contribute to a short online interview to present your profile and mission and investment in the cybersecurity sector. Share the produced interview article/video on your channels.
Original social media posts	At least 2 original posts on the selected social media channel(s) presenting your involvement with COcyber through personal thoughts and any of the Ambassador programme visuals that will be provided (e.g. banner).
Continuous support activity on social media	Likes on COcyber's posts, re-shares of COcyber posts on social media, original re-shares and comments.
Contribution to COcyber's public consultations	If the Ambassadorship is active when the COcyber team runs a public consultation on a specific topic, you are invited to provide your inputs (either via questionnaire or an interview)
COcyber-related event participation	Showcasing COcyber in online/offline events (owned or external) around cybersecurity topics. Provide visibility to COcyber by giving a presentation introducing the project or sharing the project information with participants.
Join the mid-term and final Ambassador programme online meetings	Meeting with the COcyber team to assess the status of the Ambassadorship activities and discuss the most recent project updates.

Table 1. Monitoring KPIs for the Ambassadorship

Who can be an Ambassador?

The COcyber project gathers a pool of individuals with a solid online presence and a reputation in the cybersecurity sector (for instance, through job positions, engaged organisations or ongoing projects). To be eligible for the Ambassador role, the ideal profile is as follows:

- **Professionals engaged in cybersecurity** in civilian or defence areas. They can have different professional profiles, including technical innovators, policymakers, operational practitioners, researchers, private or defence sector professionals, and other influential figures engaged in cybersecurity topics.
- **Proven activity on social media:** with at least 2,000+ followers across various platforms (e.g. LinkedIn, Mastodon, BlueSky, Instagram, or Reddit).
- **Proven online presence:** at least one reference website (e.g. the organisation website where the candidate works).
- **Proven impact:** demonstrated through recognized activities, contributions and engagement in the cybersecurity sector (e.g. scientific publications, job positions, proven technical expertise, contribution to standardisation and/or regulations, publications in specialised journals or magazines, previous mentorship or ambassadorships).

In addition, the ambassador candidates must be:

- A **European citizen** based in one of the 27 EU Member States; we aim to represent the geographical diversity of the European Union among our Ambassadors. Additionally, other criteria, such as gender, will be considered to promote greater diversity among candidates. Above **the age of legal majority**.
- An individual who is **able to sign a contract** with the project.

How are the Ambassadors selected?

Over the project's lifetime, we aim to work with 15+ dedicated professionals from different parts of Europe and target stakeholder types.

The COcyber team launches a call of interest to find interested candidates for the Ambassador programme; this call is communicated during the profile scouting phase for each batch on COcyber's communication channels. Simultaneously, the COcyber team scouts candidate profiles from different networks. All identified relevant profiles are shortlisted to an internal candidates' database, and the project's selection committee rates the profiles based on the following criteria:

- **Social media following** – a minimum of 2,000 followers across different social media platforms.

- **Fit to the position**
- **Preference:** each selection committee member can add one additional point to eight candidates of their preference.
- **Submitted expressions of interest:** candidates who submit an expression of interest receive one automatic “extra” point to acknowledge their motivation.

The highest-rated candidates are then selected, with extra profiles kept on a reserve list in case any of the selected candidates declines the offer.

When are the Ambassadors working for COcyber?

Ambassadors are recruited in 3 batches, each running for 6 months. The following figure details the months when the Ambassadors would actively collaborate with COcyber in each batch.

How do the Ambassadors benefit from their involvement in COcyber?

In exchange for their investment as an ambassador, the engaged professionals will:

- **Gain visibility** among the engaged European organisations, including the European Commission and European Cybersecurity Competence Centre, which funds our project.
- **Benefit from COcyber’s marketing services** to enrich your social media content.
- **Connect with various professionals** from civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors.
- Receive **€1,000 as financial compensation** for the successfully delivered Ambassadorship.

Is there a contract for the engaged Ambassadors?

Yes. The COcyber project provides the contract to all Ambassadors, and it is signed bilaterally at the start of the Ambassadorship between the engaged individual and the project coordinator, 28DIGITAL. Then, the financial compensation can be issued upon the delivery of a successful Ambassadorship.

How does the programme support the recruited Ambassadors?

AUSTRALO, a COcyber partner, manages the Ambassador programme, and has appointed staff members to maintain regular contact with the Ambassadors. The COcyber team will regularly inform the Ambassadors about their ongoing key project activities and results, enabling them to communicate and share these within their networks. When necessary, the COcyber team will provide support materials –such as marketing kits– to help Ambassadors easily share COcyber social media posts on their channels.

AUSTRALO also schedules at least two online meetings with the Ambassadors to discuss their activity, updates and any suggestions they might have.

Any questions?

We'll be happy to answer! You can reach us at contact@cocyber.eu.

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